

ULTRA-HIGH SPEED FULL-FIELD DEFORMATION MEASUREMENTS TO IDENTIFY THE HIGH STRAIN RATE BEHAVIOUR OF COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

It is well known that for fibre-reinforced polymeric composites, the mechanical behaviour under high rate impact is significantly different from that under static loading because of the strain rate effects. However, the measurement of modulus with current testing techniques like the so-called Split Hopkinson Pressure Bar (SHPB) is made very difficult by the presence of transient inertial effects. This has resulted in the past in conflicting conclusions about the effect of strain rate on modulus, with some reporting increase of the shear modulus with strain rate and others, a decrease. This work presents a novel methodology to accurately measure the in-plane shear modulus of composites loaded at high rates based on the use of full-field acceleration maps to provide load information, an extension to previous work on isotropic materials.

1 INTRODUCTION

Current high strain rate testing procedures of materials are limited by poor instrumentation which leads to the requirement for stringent assumptions to enable data processing and constitutive model identification. This is the case for instance for the well-known Split Hopkinson Pressure Bar (SHPB) apparatus which relies on strain gauge measurements away from the deforming sample. This paper is a step forward in the exploration of novel tests based on time and space resolved kinematic measurements obtained through ultra-high speed imaging. The underpinning idea is to use acceleration fields obtained from temporal differentiation of the full-field deformation maps measured through techniques like Digital Image Correlation (DIC) or the grid method. This information is then used for inverse identification with the Virtual fields Method.

This communication will present the general features of the method and show some examples of application in the elastic range, first for a quasi-isotropic lay-up, and then for an orthotropic unidirectional. It is mostly based on work already published in [1-2].

2 EXPERIMENTAL SET-UP

Two set-ups have been used. The first one, at the University of Oxford, uses a cylindrical projectile of diameter 34 mm and length 50 mm whereas the second set-up shown in Fig. 1 uses a smaller gas gun to launch small steel balls. The material used in this study is a carbon/epoxy made from Cytec's MTM58FRB prepreg. The nominal stiffness parameters obtained from quasi-static tests performed at the University of Southampton [3] on the UD ply are: $E_{11} = 124$ GPa, $E_{22} = 7.5$ GPa, $\nu_{12} = 0.31$, $G_{12} = 4.0$ GPa. Both $[0]_8$ (UD) and $[0/45/-45/90]_S$ (QI) lay-up were considered, all specimens being about

3.7 mm thick. The camera used in this study is a Shimadzu HPV-X. This camera enables to record a total of 128 images at a maximum interframe time of 0.2 μs , which has been used here. Finally, the grid method was used to measure displacement maps, as detailed in [1]. A grid of pitch 0.2 mm has been transferred to the specimen and spatial phase shifting used to go from grey level images to displacements. Spatial and temporal filtering was used to derive strains by spatial differentiation and acceleration by double temporal differentiation.

The idea of this test is to perform a loading/unloading test at very high strain rates. The impact generates a compressive pulse which travels along the specimen. When the wave reaches the free end, it reflects off as a tensile wave and superimposes to the incident compressive wave to gradually unload the specimens. The test lasts about 20 μs , the time for the wave to travel twice the specimen length.

Strain and acceleration maps have been processed with the Virtual Fields Method [4] to extract elastic stiffness components. Several VFM approaches have been implemented. The simplest one consists in using a rigid-body like virtual field to reconstruct average stresses through the width from averages of the acceleration [1]. This enables to extract stress-strain curves directly. The other is the general VFM approach which uses *a priori* linear elastic isotropic (for the QI) and orthotropic (for the UD) parameterization.

Figure 1: Experimental set-up with the ball impactor (from [2]).

3 RESULTS

3.1 Quasi-isotropic

Fig. 2 shows a typical stress-strain curve obtained for an impact speed of 30 $\text{m}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$ with the cylindrical specimen. The initial non-linear part of the curve comes from some spatial ‘leakage’ of the acceleration field because of the temporal smoothing. Ahead of the wave front, the smoothing generates small spurious amounts of acceleration before any significant strain is present. But this vanishes quickly and after this, the behaviour is remarkably linear and elastic, as expected as the maximum stress reached here, 300 MPa, is just below the onset of first ply damage. This is therefore a loading-unloading cycle at a strain rate of the order of 2000 s^{-1} , which is quite remarkable. The value of the modulus obtained here is about 40 GPa whereas the expected value was 47.5 GPa. This is because of the presence of transverse stresses as the impact was not uniform across the width. Assuming a Poisson’s ratio of 0.31, one can plot the σ_{xx} stress as a function of $\varepsilon_{xx} + \nu\varepsilon_{yy}$, identify Q_{xx} and retrieve E. In this case, a value of 43.5 GPa is obtained, which is within 10% of the reference value. This demonstrates the potential of the technique. More results are available in [1]. Similar results have been obtained with the ball impact tests, though strain levels were much lower [2].

Figure 2: Tress-strain curve at a strain rate of about 2000 s^{-1} for a quasi-isotropic specimen impacted at 30 m.s^{-1} with the cylindrical projectile (from [1]).

3.2 Unidirectional

Specimens have been cut at 15° and 60° to perform off-axis inertial impact tests with the cylindrical impactor. The idea here was to investigate the possibility to identify all stiffness components from a single test. This time, the simple stress-strain approach does not hold as the material is orthotropic and the full Virtual Fields Method needs to be used. Piecewise optimized virtual fields have been used to identify the four orthotropic stiffness components. This can be done for each time at which an image is recorded. It was found that only Q_{11} and Q_{66} could be identified for the 15° test as the σ_{22} stress was too small whereas at 60° , only Q_{22} and Q_{66} could be identified as the σ_{11} stress was too small. An example of result is provided in Fig. 3.

4 CONCLUSION

This paper shows that it is feasible to use acceleration maps obtained through time-resolved resolved full-field measurements, here with the grid method but Digital Image Correlation could also be employed, to identify stiffness components of composite materials, first for a simple quasi-isotropic configuration, then for an orthotropic unidirectional. This is a feasibility study, much work remains to be done. The next steps will be to make the off-axis specimen more heterogeneous so that all four stiffness components can be identified, for instance by using a notch or a hole to act as strain concentrators. This technique will also be investigated to obtain interlaminar properties. Finally, the approach will be extended to damage laws.

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Figure 3: Identification results for the 60° off-axis impacts tests, Q_{11} and Q_{12} could not be identified as the σ_{11} stress component was too small in this configuration.

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